

1. PG scholar, Master of Business Administration in Agri Business Management, School of Agri Business Management, Nagpur.
2. Head, Section of Agricultural Economics and Statistics, College of Agriculture, Nagpur.
3. PG scholar, Master of Business Administration in Agri Business Management, School of Agri Business Management, Nagpur.
manishanagre54@gmail.com

MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised: 16.09.2024; MS Accepted: 17.09.2024)

MS 3265

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRI-BUSINESS MANAGEMENT,)

Abstract

This research project provides a comprehensive appraisal of the fish seed production business, focusing on Param Krushi Udyog, Nagpur, an enterprise established in 2017 by Mr. Prabhakar Mandhare. The study analyzes various aspects of the company's operations, including the production process, cost structures, and critical factors affecting productivity and profitability. Key findings reveal that the total capital investment in the project amounted to Rs. 246.09 lakhs, with land comprising the largest share (81.27%), followed by fish tank (13%). Fixed costs totaled Rs. 104.23 lakhs, with fish tank depreciation accounting 37.86% of the total, while building depreciation constituted 8.31%. The study estimates the variable costs of production at Rs. 10.85 lakhs, primarily driven by the cost of raw materials (82.94%) and casual labours (13.27%). The total cost incurred by the producer was Rs. 115.08 lakhs, while the gross return from production was Rs. 360 lakhs, resulting in net returns of Rs. 240 lakhs. The break-even point was determined to be 35.67 lakhs units in physical terms and Rs. 107.03 lakhs in monetary terms. Marketing expenses were Rs. 0.27 lakhs, with packaging being the largest component (92.45%) followed by transportation (7.54%). Key challenges identified include difficulties in maintaining required climate and high mortality rate of fish seed. The findings emphasize the need for strategic innovation and adaptability to sustain growth and profitability in the fish seed industry.

Keywords: Business Appraisal, Financial Performance, fish seed industry, Small Business Success.

Introduction

Fish farming, or pisciculture, is the commercial breeding of fish in controlled environments to meet the growing global demand for dietary fish protein, which has led to overfishing and declining wild fish stocks. Primarily practiced in fish tanks or ponds, this aquaculture method allows for sustainable fish production while minimizing impacts on natural populations. Notably, China dominates global farmed fish production, contributing to over 50% of seafood from aquaculture as of 2016. While carnivorous species like salmon still depend on wild forage fish for feed, fish farming also supports the aquarium trade, primarily in Asia and Eastern Europe. In India, where a significant portion of the population lives in rural areas, establishing fish hatcheries could create job opportunities, reduce unemployment, and promote sustainable livelihoods using accessible technologies.

Regarding need and importance of the study, the rising global demand for fish, driven by population growth, increasing incomes, and a focus on health, has made aquaculture essential, with fish seed hatcheries playing a crucial role in providing a consistent supply of high-quality juvenile fish. This not only supports food security in developing countries, where fish is a vital protein source, but also reduces reliance on overexploited wild stocks. Additionally, fish seed hatcheries stimulate economic growth by creating jobs in rural and coastal areas and supporting related industries like fish feed production. They also aid in the conservation of endangered species and biodiversity by breeding and releasing fish into the wild, thus reducing pressure on marine ecosystems and promoting sustainable fishing practices.

The scope of study, capital requirement, cost and returns, marketing and distribution is very important and useful for following persons: Students, Researcher and Entrepreneur with regard to:

1. To identify the key strategies small business use to implement agro-processing successfully.
2. To know the profitability of company.
3. To adopt new promotional strategies for better production and sale.
4. Students can take reference from this project about making projects on business performance of any other company.
5. Researcher can take this project as reference for calculating the market share of different companies.

Company Profile

1. Name of unit: Fish seed centre at Virkhadi Tal. Kuhi, Dist. Nagpur
2. Owner Name: Mrs. Asha Prabhakar Mandhre
3. Establishment Year: 2017
4. Business Type: Agro-based industry
5. Type of ownership: Self owned

6. Address: At Post Virkhadi, Tal- Kuhi, Dist- Nagpur.

7. Initial Investment: 200 lakhs

8. Annual Turnover :120 lakhs

Objectives of study

1. To analyze the establishment cost of Param Krushi Udyog Fish Seed Hatchery.
2. To work out cost and returns of Fish Seed Production.
3. To estimate break-even point of Param Krushi Udyog Fish Seed Hatchery.
4. To study the marketing of Fish Seed.
5. To identify the constraints faced by Param Krushi Udyog Fish Seed Hatchery

Methodology

Area of Study

The present study was conducted at Param Krushi Udyog fish seed Hatchery, Nagpur.

Period of Study

The data was collected for the FY 2023-2024 i.e., from April 2023 to March 2024.

Source of Data

Primary data was collected by pretested schedule from concern person, officials of selected firm by personal interview method regarding the production and marketing.

Analytical Tools

Cost and Returns of Fish seed Production:

The collected data related to required cost and returns from Fish seed were analyzed, tabulated on the following different aspects viz.

Fixed Cost:

The fixed cost includes the data regarding the cost of machinery, building, furniture, wages of payment employed labours, salary of staff. This information was collected from Param Krushi Udyog fish seed Hatchery, Nagpur.

Variable Cost:

The variable cost consists of expenditure on purchase of raw material, wages of casual labours, repair and maintenance of machinery, electricity and stationary charges, etc.

Total Cost:

Total cost was comprised of the total fixed cost and total variable cost calculated by adding both costs together.

Total cost = Fixed cost + Variable cost

Gross Returns:

The gross returns for production of Fish seed were calculated by adding together value of main product received after production of incense sticks. The gross returns defined as the total rate of return on an investment before the deduction of any expenses.

Gross returns = Quantity of product X Price per unit

Net Returns:

The net returns refer to returns after deducting all expenses from the gross return generated by the investment.

Net returns = Gross returns – Total cost

B:C ratio:

The benefit cost ratio compares the present value of all benefits with that of the cost and investment of the project.

B:C ratio = Gross returns / Total cost

Breakeven Point Analysis:

The point at which the two curves i.e. total cost curve and total revenue curve intersect is called as breakeven point, which indicates the level of production at which neither losses money nor makes profit.

Computation in physical quantity,

$$BEP = F / (P - V)$$

Computation in monetary value,

$$BEP = F / [1 - (V/P)]$$

Where,

F = Annual fixed cost in Rs.

P = Selling price per unit in Rs.

V = Variable cost per unit in Rs.

Margin of safety:

Table No. 1 Capacity utilization of fish seed unit

Sr. No.	Particulars	Value in per lakh fingerlings	Percentage (%) share
1	Capacity of production per month in fingerlings	166.66	-
2	Capacity of unit per year	2000	100.00
3	Actual production in year 2023-24	1200	60.00

Table 1. shows that total capacity of production of unit per year is 2000 lakh fingerlings out of which 1200 lakh produced in financial year 2023-2024. Thus it is concluded that capacity utilization of selected unit is 60.00 per cent.

Table No. 2 Capital Investment for fish seed Production

Sr No.	Particular	Value (in lakhs)	Percent (%) Share
1	Investment on land	200	81.27
2	Establishment of fish pond & tank	32	13
3	Building	11.20	4.55
4	Machinery	0.75	0.30
5	Furniture & Other Appliances	1.84	0.74
6	Installation charges	0.30	0.12
	Total	246.09	100

Table 2. shows that, the total investment in capital asset in Fish seed production project was Rs. 246.09 lakhs. The investment on land was the major investment which is 200 lakhs.

Cost and returns of selected unit

To fulfill the second objectives of the study in respect of organizational study of Fish seed production the results has been obtained on cost required, returns obtained from the unit are given as under.

Table No.3 Fixed cost for Fish seed production

Sr no	Particulars	Value (Rs/Year in lakh)	Value (Rs/Lakh fingerling)	Percent (%) Share
1	Depreciation on machinery	0.212	176.67	0.20
2	Depreciation on building	8.66	7222.22	8.31
3	Depreciation on Fish tank (Fish Pond)	39.46	32888.88	37.86
4	Building (Leased Rent)	1.20	1000.00	1.15
5	Depreciation on furniture and other appliances	0.89	744.17	0.85
6	Salary of permanent labour	1.68	1400.00	1.61

Margin of Safety (in physical units) = Total output - output at BEP

Margin of Safety (in monetary value) = Total revenue - Revenue at BEP

Percentage of margin of safety = BEP / Volume of total output X 100

Marketing of Fish seed

Initially the marketing cost, market margins and price spread were calculated required for Fish seed.

Marketing Cost:

The total cost incurred by the producer involved in packaging, transportation of fish seed till it reaches to customers.

Market Margin:

It refers to difference between the prices prevailing as successive stages of marketing at given period of time.

Market Margin = Selling Price – (Purchase Price + Marketing Cost)

Constraints faced by Owner:

The different constraints in production and marketing of Fish seed were identified by personal interview method.

Results and Discussion

I. Capital Requirement of Param Krushi Udyog Fish Seed Hatchery Unit

To fulfill the first objectives of the study in respect of organizational study of the Fish seed hatchery, the results has been obtained on capital investment, summary of capacity utilization are given as under.

Capacity Utilization of Param Krushi Udyog Fish Seed Hatchery

Capital investment for Fish Seed Production

Capital investment is the acquisition of physical assets by a company or a unit for use in furthering its long-term business goals and objectives.

Fixed cost for Fish seed Production

The fixed cost for a Fish seed production project includes several essential components, such as the purchase of machinery, buildings (Leased rent), furniture. Additionally, it covers permanent labours charges and interest on the fixed capital invested in the project. These costs are crucial for establishing and maintaining the infrastructure necessary for successful Fish seed production operations.

7	Interest on fixed capital	52.11	43431.93	50
	Total	104.23	86863.87	100

Table 3. shows that total fixed cost requirement for Fish seed production project was Rs. 104.23lakhs. It is observed that depreciation on fish tank was major which constituted 39.46 lakhs.

Variable cost required for Incense sticks Production

The variable cost consists of expenditure on purchase of raw material, wages of casual labour, repair and maintenance of machinery, postage, and stationery etc.

Table No. 4 Variable cost for Fish seed production

Sr.No.	Particulars	Value (Rs/Year in lakh)	Value (Rs/Lakh fingerlings)	Percent (%) Share
1	Cost of raw materials	9	7500.00	82.94
2	Casual labour charges	1.44	0.00	13.27
3	Repair and maintenance	0.3	250.00	2.76
4	Oil & Lubricant	0.01	8.33	0.09
5	Postage, stationary and telephone charges	0.1	83.33	0.92
	Total	10.85	7841.67	100

Table 4. reveals that the variable cost for Fish seed production worked out to Rs. 10.85 lakhs. The composition of variable cost revealed that the cost of raw materials was major which was 9 lakhs.

Total cost incurred by producer for production of Fish seed

Total cost incurred by producer for production of Fish seed is the sum of fixed cost and variable cost incurred by producer.

Table No. 5 Total cost incurred by producer for production and marketing of Fish Seed

Sr. No.	Particulars	Value (Rs/Year in lakh)	Value (Rs/Lakh Fingerlings)	Percent (%) Share
1	Fixed cost	104.23	86863.87	90.36
2	Variable cost	10.85	7841.67	9.40
	Total	115.08	94705.54	100

Table 5. reveals that, the total cost incurred by producer was estimated Rs. 115.08 lakhs.

Economics of production of Fish Seed production

It explores the financial aspects of Fish Seed production, focusing on production costs, revenue, and profitability. By evaluating these

economic factors, it provides insights into the financial viability and sustainability of fish seed production as a business by calculating the benefit cost ratio

Table No. 6 Economics of fish seed production project

Sr no	Particulars	Value for year in lakhs	Value for per lakh fingerlings (in lakh)
1	Production (in numbers)	120	-
2	Gross returns (Rs)	360	3
3	Total cost incurred by producer (Rs)	115.08	0.96
4	Net returns (Rs)	240	2
5	Benefit cost ratio (1:_)	1:1.30	1:1.30

Table 6. shows that, the value of product i.e., Gross return from the Product is Rs. 360 lakh, calculated by multiplying quantity of product with price per lakh fingerlings with total cost of 115.08 lakhs, the net return was 240 lakhs. The benefit cost ratio was 1:1.30 reflecting the ratio of total return to total costs.

The break-even point is the number of Fish seed produced to cover all costs associated with the production process, including both fixed and variable expenses. It is the level at which the total revenue from sell of Fish seed matches the total costs incurred, meaning that no profit or loss is achieved.

Break-even point analysis

Table No. 7 Break Even point analysis for production of fish seed

Sr. No.	Particulars	Value in lakhs
1	Actual quantity produced per year per lakh fingerlings	120
2	Annual fixed cost (Rs) F	10.42
3	Selling price per lakh fingerlings (Rs) P	3
4	Variable cost per lakh fingerlings (Rs) V	7841.67
5	Breakeven point [physical quantity] fingerlings	35.67
6	Breakeven point [monetary value] Rs	107.03
7	Margin of Safety [physical quantity] lakhs	119.99
8	Margin of Safety [monetary value] Rs Lakh	120
9	Percentage of margin of safety (%)	99.99

Table 7. reveals that, the Param Krushi Udyog Fish Seed Hatchery have to produce at least 35.67 lakh fingerlings that will recover their fixed cost and variable cost i.e., zero profit for running the unit. In monetary terms, breakeven point analysed was Rs. 107.03 lakh. Percentage of margin of safety was 99.99.

Marketing of fish seed

Marketing cost of fish seed

The marketing cost consists of cost of packaging, transportation charges, etc. required for the selling of fingerlings to the farmer.

Table No. 8 Marketing cost of fish seed

Sr.No	Particulars	Value (Rs/Year in lakhs)	Value (Rs/lakh fingerlings)	Percentage Share (%)
1	Packaging Cost	0.25	208.33	92.45
2	Transportation Cost	0.02	17	7.54
	Total	0.27	225.33	100

Table 8. shows that, the total marketing cost required for marketing of Fish seed was Rs. 0.27 Lakhs. The cost required for packaging was major which was 0.25 lakhs.

Constraints faced by Param Krushi Udyog fish seed hatchery

Table No. 12 Constraints faced by owner in production of fish seed

Sr. No.	Particulars	Rank
1	Maintaining the required climate	I
2	High mortality rate	II
3	Challenging in quality of fingerlings	III
4	Irregular electrical supply during peak production season	IV
5	Unavailability of skilled labour	V

Fish seed hatchery faces various constraints when it comes to production and marketing. These constraints can impact the efficiency and success of their operations. Here are some main constraints

Conclusion

The appraisal of Fish seed production project revealed that the total investment in capital asset in fingerlings production was Rs. 246.09 lakhs. The investment on land was the major investment followed by fish pond which individually shared, about 81.27 and 13 per cent respectively.

The total fixed cost requirement for fingerlings was Rs. 104.23 lakhs. It is observed that depreciation on fish pond accounted 37.86 per cent followed by building which constituted 8.31 per cent.

The total variable cost for fingerlings worked out to Rs. 10.85 lakhs. The composition of variable cost revealed that the cost of raw materials was 82.94 per cent followed by casual labour charges 13.27 per cent. The total marketing cost required for marketing of fingerlings was Rs. 0.27 lakhs. The cost required for packaging was major which was Rs. 0.25 lakhs i.e., 92.45 per cent followed by transportation 7.54 per cent. The total cost incurred by producer was estimated Rs. 115.08 lakhs. The maximum cost share was for fixed cost which accounts 90.36 per cent. The per cent share of variable cost was 9.40 per cent followed by marketing cost which was 0.23 per cent.

The gross return from fingerlings was 360 lakhs and the net returns 240 lakhs.

The break-even point in physical terms was 35.67 lakhs and in monetary terms 107.03 lakh.

The major constraint in production of fingerlings was maintaining required climate followed by higher mortality rate and challenging in quality of fingerlings.

Acknowledgments

I sincerely express my gratitude to my guide and mentors for their valuable guidance and support throughout the research. Their insights and encouragement were instrumental in the successful completion of this research paper.

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